

FAIRsFAIR Data Object Assessment Metrics

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Versioning History

Version	Date	Notes
0.8	13 March 2025	A major revision of the FAIRsFAIR metrics in response to a variety of publications analysing the FAIRsFAIR and other metrics as well as on feedback given by the user community. Further, experiences from developing discipline specific metrics have been taken into account. Version 0.7 skipped since this is the number of the software assessment metric using it again might cause confusion.
0.5	8 March 2022	The specification now also includes a definition of compliance (maturity) levels (0-3) for each metric. A draft of this version of the metrics has been published as appendix of deliverable 4.5 (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5336159). The current version contains a corrigendum with respect to FsF-I1-02M which was wrongly attributed to the I1 principle during the transition from v0.3 to v0.4 (see below). Instead it clearly is a I2 principle and has to be relabelled to 'FsF-I2-01M'
0.4	12 October 2020	This specification includes 17 metrics. Two metrics representing the principle A1 have been added into the specification. Metric descriptions (e.g., related resources, comments) were refined based on feedback received from external users and pilot repositories.
0.3	10 July 2020	This specification contains 15 metrics. The metric (FsF-I1-01M) from v0.2 was divided into two metrics (FsF-I1-01M and FsF-I1-02M). Metrics were improved/updated based on the focus group-based evaluation and the final version of the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model (https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00050). Specification Link: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3934401
0.2	30 April 2020	Metrics were refined based on the feedback provided by FAIRsFAIR partners. New metric (FsF-R1.2-01M Data Provenance) is added to the specification, sums up to a total of 14 metrics. Specification Link: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3775794
0.1	25 February 2020	Includes 13 metrics to assess the FAIRness of data objects, which were developed based on existing work (FAIRdat/FAIREnough, WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fit Checklist and RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model v0.03). Specification Link (Appendix II): https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3678715

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1. Introduction

The overall goal of FAIRsFAIR¹ was to develop practical solutions to facilitate the application of the FAIR principles² throughout the research data life cycle. Major outcomes of FAIRsFAIR were domain agnostic FAIR metrics and tools to support the assessment of FAIR digital objects. This work has been continued during the FAIR-IMPACT project which focussed on FAIR assessments in a discipline specific context.

While FAIR principles may apply to any digital objects, we are concerned with the subset of digital objects: research data³ that are collected, measured, or created for purposes of scientific analysis. A research data object⁴ may comprise data, metadata, and documentation (such as policies and procedures). These components influence the implementation of the FAIR assessment. For instance, they can either be resources to be evaluated or evidence of enabling FAIR.

The metrics are developed in stages, and are based on indicators proposed by the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group⁵, in addition to prior work conducted by the project partners such as FAIRdat⁶ and FAIREnough⁷, and WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use checklist⁸. We have evaluated and improved the metrics, for example through focus groups, internal reviews, public feedback, and tools (F-UJI⁹, FAIR-Aware¹⁰) implemented to support FAIR assessment in selected use cases.¹¹

Since a number of publications have used and evaluated the previously published FAIRsFAIR FAIR metrics and provided a number of significant and useful suggestions and comments on these metrics we decided to revise and publish an updated version of the FAIRsFAIR metrics.

1.1 Purpose

As mentioned above, a number of papers have recently been published that have dealt intensively with FAIR metrics used by various projects and assessment tools. In particular, the authors of these papers have rightly pointed out discrepancies between the different metrics in terms of the FAIR principles covered, their different weightings, as well as different interpretations of the FAIR principles underlying these metrics (see e.g. Gehlen et al. 2022, Sun et al, 2022, Aguilar, 2023, Moser et al., 2023 and Candela et al, 2024). A detailed comparative analyses of metrics and tests for each FAIR principle have been provided by Sun et al, 2022 , Moser et al., 2023, Aguilar, 2023 and

¹ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/>

² <https://www.force11.org/group/fairgroup/fairprinciples>

³ <http://www.rdm.kit.edu/english/research.php>

⁴ In this specification, we use the terms 'data object' and 'dataset' synonymously.

⁵ RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model Working Group (2020). FAIR Data Maturity Model: specification and guidelines. Research Data Alliance. DOI: 10.15497/RDA00050

⁶ Research Data Journal - FAIR Data Review,

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSd8_pd2r2SniCVfCC3CHhEUHZzv2MTRC3RTh0S2YTvVj87Q/viewform

⁷ <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSf7t1Z9IOBoj5GgWqik8KnhtH3B819Ch6ID5KuAz7yn0IOOpw/viewform>

⁸ Austin, C., Cousijn, H., Diepenbroek, M., Petters, J., Soares E Silva, M. (2019). WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG Outputs and Recommendations. DOI: 10.15497/rda00034

⁹ <https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/fuji>

¹⁰ <https://fairaware.dans.knaw.nl/>

¹¹ Experiences on adapting the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model are elaborated in Devaraju et al. (2020), 'From Conceptualization to Implementation: FAIR Assessment of Research Data Objects', Data Science Journal: Special Collection on Research Data Alliance Results (under review).

Candela et al, 2024 which revealed considerable differing FAIR metric coverage between several tools and their metrics respectively. Candela et al, 2024 have shown in detail which metrics of each assessment tool deviate from the FAIR principles they claimed to test. These authors have also correctly criticized that many metrics and their implementations are actually better suited to assess data quality than FAIRness. In addition, we received numerous valuable feedback and suggestions with respect to the metrics and their implementation either via F-UJI's Github page or personal communication. In addition, the revision of the metrics was informed by experience gained from the creation of discipline-specific metrics, which showed, for example, that assessments of subject-specific content in particular are too strongly associated with data quality checks which is not advisable.

As a consequence, we have significantly revised the FAIRsFAIR metrics to achieve better comparability with other metrics. In addition, we have tried to focus the metrics as much as possible on the essential spirit of the FAIR principles which includes:

- Focus on FAIR instead of data and metadata quality or veracity
- Emphasis on the dataset level, not the repository level
- Completeness and balance in the coverage of the FAIR principles

The revised metrics presented here will affect the behavior of the associated tests and their execution in comparison to previous versions, which include:

- F1: Persistent identifiers no longer are tested for resolution (e.g. HTTP status 20x), instead redirection (e.g. 30x) is tested to distinguish identifier-like strings from managed identifiers.
- F2: Methods to expose metadata no longer is tested here
- F3: Content related metadata is no longer inspected here instead this is tested in R1.
- F4: Verification whether a resource is registered in search engines has been suspended as no comprehensive and reliable APIs (e.g. Google, Bing) are available.
- A1: While the specification access conditions is not part of the published FAIR principles, it is required by the RDA metrics. Therefore this metric remains but veracity and use of dedicated data access/rights vocabularies is no longer tested
- A1: Retrievability of data and metadata is explicitly tested.
- A1.1: A dedicated metric and tests data and metadata protocol standards have been specified.
- A1.2: A dedicated metric and tests data and metadata protocol authentication have been specified.
- R1: Data-related metadata information, e.g. whether file sizes have been specified correctly, is no longer validated.
- R1.1 Validation of given licenses(e.g. using SPDX registry) is suspended.
- R1.3 Information which has been retrieved from re3data is no longer used in metric tests since this information may not be valid for every single dataset of a given repository.

Detailed justifications and explanations for all metric changes with reference to the community contributions and related publications considered are given in the **Appendix**.

In this specification (v0.8) we present 17 revised minimum viable metrics to systematically measure the extent to which research data objects are FAIR.

1.2 Metric Outline

The metrics are specified following the template (Table 1), modified from Wilkinson et al. (2018)¹². In each metric table, we provide the descriptions and assessment details of the metric, and its alignment with the relevant FAIR principle and CoreTrustSeal requirement(s).

Table 1. Modified Metric Template

Field	Description
Metric Identifier	The local (FAIRsFAIR) identifier of the metric (for more details, see Figure 1).
Metric Name	Metric name in a human readable form.
Description	The definition of the metric, including examples.
FAIR Principle	The FAIR principle most related to the metric.
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	The CoreTrustSeal requirement(s) most related to the metric.
Assessment	Requirements and methods to perform the assessment against the metric.
Comments	A list of related resources which may be used as a reference basis to implement the assessment, constraints and limitations of the proposed assessment.

Each of the FAIRsFAIR metrics is identified following a naming convention. For example, in Figure 1, the identifier starts with the shortened form of the project's name, followed by the related FAIR principle identifier and local identifier. The last part of the identifier distinguishes the resource that will be evaluated based on the metric, e.g., data or metadata.

Figure 1. Anatomy of FAIRsFAIR metric identifier.

¹² Wilkinson, MD., Sansone, SA., Schultes, E., Doorn, P., Bonino da Silva Santos, LO., Dumontier, M. (2018). A design framework and exemplar metrics for FAIRness. *Sci Data*. 2018;5:180118. DOI:10.1038/sdata.2018.118

The following is a list of the revised 17 FAIRsFAIR data assessment metrics .

Table 2. List of Metrics.

Identifier	Name
FsF-F1-01D	Data is assigned a globally unique identifier.
FsF-F1-02D	Data is assigned a persistent identifier.
FsF-F2-01M	Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.
FsF-F3-01M	Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.
FsF-F4-01M	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved by machines.
FsF-A1-01M	Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.
FsF-A1-02M	Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
FsF-A1-03D	Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol
FsF-A2-01M	Metadata remains available, even if the data is no longer available.
FsF-I1-01M	Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.
FsF-I2-01M	Metadata uses semantic resources.
FsF-I3-01M	Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.
FsF-R1-01MD	Metadata specifies the content of the data.
FsF-R1.1-01M	Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.
FsF-R1.2-01M	Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.
FsF-R1.3-01M	Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.
FsF-R1.3-02D	Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.

2. Metric Specification

2.1 Globally Unique Identifier

FIELD	DESCRIPTION						
Metric Identifier	FsF-F1-01MD						
Metric Name	Metadata and data are assigned a globally unique identifier						
Description	A globally unique identifier may be assigned to a landing page containing metadata, a metadata file or a data file or stream such that it can be referenced unambiguously by humans or machines. Globally unique means an identifier should be associated with only one resource at any time. Examples of unique identifiers are Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI), Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) such as URL. Well known persistent identifiers also are globally unique such as URN, Digital Object Identifier (DOI), the Handle System, identifiers.org, w3id.org and Archival Resource Key (ARK). Unique identifiers not necessarily are resolvable but may also be represented by a UUID (Universal Unique Identifier) or a Hash code. A data repository may assign a globally unique identifier to your metadata when you publish and make it available through their services.						
Background	While today most identifiers can be represented as actionable URLs still some non-actionable identifiers may in be in use which are globally unique such as UUID (Philipson, 2017) ¹³						
FAIR Principle	F1. (Meta) data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers						
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R13. The repository enables users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation						
ASSESSMENT							
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dataset and/or metadata (incl. landing page) identifier List of globally unique identifier schemes 						
Associated F-UJI tests	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Metadata identifier follows a defined unique identifier syntax or scheme (IRI, URL, UUID, HASH or PID)</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Data identifier follows a defined unique identifier syntax (IRI, URL, UUID, HASH or PID)</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Metadata identifier follows a defined unique identifier syntax or scheme (IRI, URL, UUID, HASH or PID)	1	Data identifier follows a defined unique identifier syntax (IRI, URL, UUID, HASH or PID)	0
test	score						
Metadata identifier follows a defined unique identifier syntax or scheme (IRI, URL, UUID, HASH or PID)	1						
Data identifier follows a defined unique identifier syntax (IRI, URL, UUID, HASH or PID)	0						
Scoring mechanism	cumulative, total metric score is calculated as the sum of all test scores						
Method	Check if the identifier is specified based on a globally unique identifier scheme. For both, data as well as metadata specific tests can be specified. We decided to score only if GUIDs for metadata are found for backwards compatibility reasons.						
Pass/Fail criterion	Metric test is passed if a unique identifier for metadata or landing page has been found.						
COMMENTS							
Distinction between data and metadata sometimes is not possible, therefore second test is not scored							

¹³Philipson, J. (2019). Identifying PIDs Playing FAIR. Data Science, vol. 2, no. 1-2, pp. 229-244. doi:10.3233/DS-190024

Related Resources:

- Identifiers compiled by FAIRsharing, https://fairsharing.org/standards/?q=&selected_facets=type_exact:identifier%20schema
- A list of Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) schemes, available in different formats, <https://www.iana.org/assignments/uri-schemes/uri-schemes.xhtml#uri-schemes-1>
- Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) Generic Syntax (RFC 3986), <https://tools.ietf.org/html/rfc3986>

2.2 Persistent Identifier

FIELD	DESCRIPTION								
Metric Identifier	FsF-F1-02MD								
Metric Name	Metadata and data are assigned a persistent identifier.								
Description	Both, metadata as well as data, should be provided with a persistent identifier. We make a distinction between the uniqueness and persistence of an identifier: An HTTP URL (the address of a given unique resource on the web) is globally unique, but may not be persistent as the URL of data may be not accessible (link rot problem) or the data available under the original URL may be changed (content drift problem). Identifiers based on the Handle System, DOI, ARK are both globally unique and persistent. They are maintained and governed such that they remain stable and resolvable for the long term. The persistent identifier (PID) may be resolved (point) to a landing page, metadata or the data content (downloadable artefact), or none if the data or repository is no longer maintained. Therefore, ensuring persistence is a shared responsibility between a PID service provider (e.g., datacite) and its clients (e.g., data repositories). For example, the DOI system guarantees the persistence of its identifiers through its social (e.g., policy) and technical infrastructures, whereas a data provider ensures the availability of the resource (e.g., landing page, downloadable artefact) associated with the identifier.								
Background	The EOSC PID policy requires a PID to be globally unique, persistent, and resolvable (Valle et al., 2020). No authoritative list or registry of persistent identifiers yet exists, but the DataCite identifier type vocabulary (DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2019) is listing most common PID types. These can be used except identifiers exclusively used for print products and physical entities (e.g., ISBN, EAN, ROR). In addition, identifiers listed in identifiers.org which provides a resolver service for these can be used to complement the controlled list.								
FAIR Principle	F1. (Meta) data are assigned globally unique and persistent identifiers								
CoreTrustSeal alignment	R13. The repository enables users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation								
ASSESSMENT									
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dataset and/or metadata (including landing page) identifier • List of commonly accepted persistent identifiers for data 								
Associated F-UJ tests	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Metadata identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax</td> <td>0.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Persistent identifier for metadata is registered and maintained by a PID authority</td> <td>0.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Data identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Metadata identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax	0.5	Persistent identifier for metadata is registered and maintained by a PID authority	0.5	Data identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax	0
test	score								
Metadata identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax	0.5								
Persistent identifier for metadata is registered and maintained by a PID authority	0.5								
Data identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax	0								

	Persistent identifier for data is registered and maintained by a PID authority	0
Scoring mechanism	cumulative, total metric score is calculated as the sum of all test scores	
Method	<p>Check if the data identifier specified is based on a commonly accepted persistent identifier scheme and syntax, and if it is registered by a PID authority (verified by redirection of the original PID IRI representation) which distinguishes PID-like strings from real PIDs.</p> <p>For both, data as well as metadata, specific tests can be specified. We decided to score only if PIDs for metadata are found for backwards compatibility reasons.</p>	
Pass/Fail criterion	Metric test is passed if a persistent identifier for metadata or landing page has been found.	
COMMENTS		
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A wiki entry on persistent identifier, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Persistent_identifier • Generic PID definitions, Initial Persistent Identifier Policy for the EOSC, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3574202 • FREYA Deliverable 3.1 (Survey of Current PID Services Landscape), https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1324295 • FREYA Deliverable 2.1 PID Resolution Services Best Practices, https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1324299 <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A registry of persistent identifiers should provide the list of identifiers as well as associated policy documents for ensuring persistence that may be periodically reviewed and updated. If a policy document is issued with a validity period, this should be captured by the registry. • A PID service provider may periodically check if an identifier within its registry is resolvable (e.g., https://support.datacite.org/docs/link-checker). While the PID itself may be persistent, it may not resolve to a downloadable artefact if the data or repository is no longer maintained. • Some PID resolution services such as w3id or identifiers.org do not register individual PIDs but e.g repository specific PID ranges or PID patterns only. • Distinction between data and metadata sometimes is not possible. 		

2.3 Descriptive Core Metadata

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-F2-01M
Metric Name	Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.
Description	Metadata is descriptive information about a data object. Since the metadata required differs depending on the users and their applications, this metric focuses on core metadata. The core metadata is the minimum descriptive information required to enable data finding, including citation which makes it easier to find data. We determine the required metadata based on common data citation

	<p>guidelines (e.g., DataCite¹⁴, ESIP¹⁵, and IASSIST¹⁶), and metadata recommendations for data discovery (e.g., EOSC Datasets Minimum Information (EDMI)¹⁷, DataCite Metadata Schema, W3C Recommendation Data on the Web Best Practices and Data Catalog Vocabulary).</p> <p>This metric focuses on domain-agnostic core metadata but may also include the analysis of domain specific metadata properties. A repository should adopt a schema that includes properties of core metadata, whereas data authors should take the responsibility of providing core metadata.</p>								
Background	<p>Following data citation guidelines (Data Citation Synthesis Group, 2014¹⁸, Ball & Duke, 2015¹⁹; Mooney & Newton, 2012²⁰ and Fenner et al., 2019²¹) metadata properties necessary for proper data citation are: <i>creator, title, publication date, publisher, and identifier</i>.</p> <p>In addition, abstract or summary and keywords are essential to enable discoverability and the indication of a resource type is necessary to distinguish research data objects from other digital objects (Fenner et al. ,2019²⁴).</p> <p>The resulting set of core descriptive metadata elements (creator, title, publisher, publication date, summary, keywords, identifier) aligns well with existing recommendations for data discovery and core metadata definition (Asmi et al., 2017²¹, DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2019²², Loscio et al., 2017²³ and Albertoni et al., 2020²⁴). This set of metadata elements is present in most domain agnostic metadata standards such as Dublin Core, DCAT-2, schema.org/Dataset, and DataCite schema.</p>								
FAIR Principle	F2. Data are described with rich metadata								
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R13. The repository enables users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation								
ASSESSMENT									
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Dataset identifier (IRI, URL) ● Machine-accessible and readable metadata 								
Associated F-UJI tests	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Core data citation metadata is available</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">or</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Core descriptive metadata is available</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Core data citation metadata is available	1	or		Core descriptive metadata is available	2
test	score								
Core data citation metadata is available	1								
or									
Core descriptive metadata is available	2								

¹⁴ DataCite Metadata Working Group. 2019. "DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data. Version 4.3." DataCite e.V. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.14454/7xq3-zf69>.

¹⁵ ESIP Data Preservation and Stewardship Committee. 2019. "Data Citation Guidelines for Earth Science Data, Version 2." ESIP. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.8441816.v1>.

¹⁶ <https://iassistdata.org/community/data-citation-ig/data-citation-resources/>

¹⁷ Asmi, A., B. Cordewener, C. Goble, D. Castelli, E. Kühn, F. Pasian, F. Niccolucci, et al. 2017. "D6.6: 2nd Report on Data Interoperability." EOSCpilot. <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5b5bdb1165&appId=PPGMS>.

¹⁸ Data Citation Synthesis Group. 2014. "Joint Declaration of Data Citation Principles." Edited by Mercè Crosas. FORCE11. <https://doi.org/10.25490/a97f-egyk>.

¹⁹ <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/guidance/how-guides/cite-datasets>

²⁰ Mooney, Hailey, and Mark P. Newton. 2012. "The Anatomy of a Data Citation: Discovery, Reuse, and Credit." *Journal of Librarianship and Scholarly Communication* 1 (1): 1035.

²¹ Fenner, Martin, Mercè Crosas, Jeffrey S. Grethe, David Kennedy, Henning Hermjakob, Phillippe Rocca-Serra, Gustavo Durand, et al. 2019. "A Data Citation Roadmap for Scholarly Data Repositories." *Scientific Data* 6 (1): 28.

²² DataCite Metadata Working Group. 2019. "DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data. Version 4.3." DataCite e.V. 2019. <https://doi.org/10.14454/7xq3-zf69>.

²³ Lóscio, B. F., C. Burle, and N. Calegari. 2017. "Data on the Web Best Practices." W3C Recommendation. The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). <https://www.w3.org/TR/dwbp>.

²⁴ Albertoni, R., S. Cox, A. Gonzalez Beltran, A. Perego, and P. Winstanley. 2020. "Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) - Version 2." W3C Recommendation. The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

Scoring mechanism	alternative, total metric score is equal to highest individual test score reached
Method	<p>Use the data identifier to access its metadata document. Parse or retrieve core metadata, e.g., through one or more options below, combine the results and then verify presence/absence of the core elements in the metadata.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Structured data embedded in the landing page of the identifier (e.g., Schema.org, Dublin Core and OpenGraph meta tags) ● Typed Links in the HTTP Link header; for more information, see https://signposting.org/conventions/ ● Content negotiation (including external negotiation services offered by PID providers) <p>Check if data citation metadata is available. Check if core descriptive metadata is available.</p>
Pass/Fail criterion	Metric test is passed if core data citation metadata has been found.
COMMENTS	
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Examples of metadata recommendations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ EOSC EDM metadata properties, https://eosc-edmi.github.io/properties ○ W3C Recommendation Data on the Web Best Practices, https://www.w3.org/TR/dwbp/#metadata ○ W3C Data Catalog Vocabulary, https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/ ● Sites that provide a list of metadata standards: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ FAIRsharing, https://fairsharing.org/standards/ ○ RDA Metadata Directory (General Research Data Standards), https://rd-alliance.github.io/metadata-directory/subjects/general.html ● Examples of domain agnostic metadata standards for describing research data: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) Metadata Terms, https://www.w3.org/TR/dwbp/#bib-DCTERMS ○ DataCite Metadata Schema, https://doi.org/10.14454/7xq3-zf69 ○ Schema.org, https://schema.org/Dataset ○ Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT), https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/ <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The assessment assumes that the identifier resolves to a landing page (e.g., html) that contains the metadata of the data. Landing page may not necessarily be an html page. ● Data providers may use a variety of different standards to expose the metadata of their data which needs to be parsed. ● The metadata records maintained by a data provider might not be accessible, due to, e.g., broken link of the landing page, proprietary metadata standard used, and restricted metadata. 	

2.4 Inclusion of Data Identifier in Metadata

FIELD	DESCRIPTION				
Metric Identifier	FsF-F3-01M				
Metric Name	Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes.				
Description	The metadata should explicitly specify the identifier of the data (content) such that users can discover and access the data through the metadata. Such identifiers could, for example, be represented by links to downloadable data files but also to services that enable a selection of data.				
FAIR Principle	F3: Metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data they describe				
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R13. The repository enables users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation				
ASSESSMENT					
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data identifier (IRI, URL) Machine-accessible and readable metadata 				
Associated F-UJI tests	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	1
test	score				
Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	1				
Method	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use the dataset identifier to access its metadata document. Check if the identifier (link) to access data content is included in the metadata (e.g., use the metadata elements like 'schema:Distribution' or Typed Links). 				
Pass/Fail criterion	Metric test is passed if at least one data identifiers has been found in the metadata or if a signposting 'item' link has been found				
COMMENTS					
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Signposting the Scholarly Web, https://signposting.org/conventions/ FAIR Signposting Profile, https://signposting.org/FAIR/ <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A metadata standard may not support any element or include multiple elements through which a data identifier may be specified. Identifiers may indicate alternative distribution channels of a given dataset which may rather represent different versions of the dataset. 					

2.5 Searchable Metadata

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-F4-01M
Metric Name	Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be registered or indexed by search engines.
Description	Metadata can be available via multiple endpoints. For example, a repository may distribute its metadata via a metadata protocol (e.g. via OAI-PMH) and/or a custom web service, but these may only support specialized catalogs that are only known to a limited number of people. This metric focuses on those methods of making metadata available that are beneficial to as many user groups as possible, i.e. that

	can be consumed by well-known, large catalogs and search engines such as Google and Bing. Such metadata should be offered according to the requirements of these search engines.				
FAIR Principle	F4. (Meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource				
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R13. The repository enables users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation				
ASSESSMENT					
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dataset identifier (IRI, URL) 				
Associated F-UJI tests	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Metadata is given in a way major search engines can ingest it for their catalogues (Dublin Core or schema.org or DCAT encoded in microdata, RDFa, embedded JSON-LD or meta tags see e.g. Google Dataset Search webmaster guidelines)</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Metadata is given in a way major search engines can ingest it for their catalogues (Dublin Core or schema.org or DCAT encoded in microdata, RDFa, embedded JSON-LD or meta tags see e.g. Google Dataset Search webmaster guidelines)	2
test	score				
Metadata is given in a way major search engines can ingest it for their catalogues (Dublin Core or schema.org or DCAT encoded in microdata, RDFa, embedded JSON-LD or meta tags see e.g. Google Dataset Search webmaster guidelines)	2				
Assessment	<p>The following methods may be applied to determine if metadata of the data is accessible programmatically:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Check if the metadata provision endpoint returns search engine friendly metadata records based on a request using the data identifier (see comment* below) 				
Pass/Fail criterion	Metric test is passed if metadata is provided as Dublin Core or schema.org or DCAT encoded in microdata, RDFa, embedded JSON-LD or meta tags format.				
COMMENTS					
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Google webmaster guidelines, https://developers.google.com/search/docs/essentials Bing webmaster guidelines, https://www.bing.com/webmasters/help/webmaster-guidelines-30fba23a Google reference documentation on representing structured data of Dataset, https://developers.google.com/search/docs/data-types/dataset <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Structured data may be provided in different formats, JSON-LD, RDFa or Microdata which may change over time. The variety of formats should be handled as part of the assessment. Embedding structured data does not guarantee that the data will be present on search results. To verify that the data is findable through a web search engine, however, most of the web search engine do not offer an API at all (Google Dataset Search) or APIs (e.g., Google Custom Search, Bing Web Search API) offer a limited selection of their index or limited number of free search queries. 					

2.6 Data Access Information

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-A1-01M
Metric Name	Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.
Description	This metric determines if the metadata includes the level of access to the data such as public, embargoed, restricted, or metadata-only access and its access conditions. Both access level and conditions are necessary information to potentially gain access to the data. It is recommended that data should be as open as possible and as closed as necessary. Datasets should be released into the public domain and openly accessible without restrictions when possible. Embargoed

	access refers to data that will be made publicly accessible at a specific date which should be specified in the metadata. Restricted access refers to data that can be accessed under certain conditions or is available to a particular group of users or after permission is granted.					
FAIR Principle	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communication protocol Note: This metric is about ensuring provision of metadata related to data access and based on metric RDA-A1-01. This metadata is important to retrieve data using a standardized communication protocol, thus we mapped it to the principle A1.					
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R2. The repository maintains all applicable licenses covering data access and use and monitors compliance R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community					
ASSESSMENT						
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dataset identifier (IRI, URL) Machine-accessible and readable metadata 					
Associated F-UJI tests	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Information about access restrictions or rights can be identified in metadata</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Information about access restrictions or rights can be identified in metadata	1	
test	score					
Information about access restrictions or rights can be identified in metadata	1					
Assessment	Use the data identifier to access its metadata document. Check the presence/absence of data access level or access conditions through appropriate metadata element(s).					
Pass/Fail criterion	Metric test is passed if access conditions are found in metadata					
COMMENTS						
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public domain licenses, https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain EU Vocabulary on access rights, https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/at-dataset/-/resource/dataset/access-right Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) Information Model 2.2, https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/ Controlled Vocabulary for Access Rights, http://vocabularies.coar-repositories.org/documentation/access_rights/ Archival Access Rights Vocabulary (test vocabulary, not yet available through the production metadata registry), http://sandbox.metadataregistry.org/concept/list/vocabulary_id/251.html Eprints Access Rights Vocabulary Encoding Scheme, http://www.ukoln.ac.uk/repositories/digirep/index/Eprints_AccessRights_Vocabulary_Encoding_Scheme <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The metadata standard considered as part of the assessment may not include all of the elements for representing data access levels and related access information. The access information may be expressed in an unstructured manner, e.g., as a 'comment' in the metadata document. The assessment of this metric only checks the metadata of access restrictions, but it does not validate if the access conditions specified are correct. A data object may consist of several files with different access levels; some are with open access while others are with restricted access. So mixed access levels may apply to the object. 						

2.7 Retrievable Metadata and Data

FIELD	DESCRIPTION						
Metric Identifier	FsF-A1-02MD						
Metric Name	Metadata and data are retrievable by their identifier						
Description	This metric determines whether data and metadata are accessible via their identifiers, i.e. whether the identifiers resolve to a target that actually contains data or metadata.						
FAIR Principle	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communication protocol						
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community.						
ASSESSMENT							
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dataset identifier (IRI, URL) Data identifier 						
Associated F-UJI tests	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th><th>score</th></tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Metadata are retrievable via their specified identifier</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr> <td>Data are retrievable via the identifiers given in metadata</td><td>1</td></tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Metadata are retrievable via their specified identifier	1	Data are retrievable via the identifiers given in metadata	1
test	score						
Metadata are retrievable via their specified identifier	1						
Data are retrievable via the identifiers given in metadata	1						
Assessment	It is checked whether identifiers are actionable and successfully resolve to a target that actually contains data or metadata.						
COMMENTS							
<p>This metric specifically assesses the ‘retrievability’ aspect of A1. This metric also includes the retrievability of metadata which cannot be parsed or data formats and services which may not be known by the assessment service. Therefore this metric is independent from the above defined F-principle related metrics.</p> <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Retrievability can be intentionally restricted for a variety of reasons. 							

2.8 Standard Communication Protocol of Metadata and Data

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-A1.1-01MD
Metric Name	A standardized communication protocol is used to access metadata and data
Description	Given an identifier of a dataset, the metadata of the dataset as well as related data should be retrievable using a standard communication protocol such as HTTP, HTTPS, FTP, TFTP, SFTP, FTAM etc. Avoid disseminating data using a proprietary protocol.
FAIR Principle	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communication protocol
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community.
ASSESSMENT	
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data identifier (IRI, URL)

Associated F-UJI tests	test	score
	Identifier leading to metadata matches a scheme indicating a standardized web communication protocol	1
	Identifier leading to data are matching a schema indicating a standardized web communication protocol	1
Scoring mechanism	cumulative, total metric score is calculated as the sum of all test scores	
Assessment	Use the metadata and/or data identifier to identify the application protocol used to serve the content based on the scheme part of the IRI. In case external metadata is linked to the landing page by typed links, use the data identifier specified in the typed link.	
COMMENTS		
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examples of application layer protocols, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Application_layer IANA Protocol Registries, https://www.iana.org/protocols <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The metadata of a dataset may be shared in different ways (landing page, dedicated API, link relation type). The assessment assumes that the identifier resolves to metadata or a landing page (e.g., html) that contains the metadata of the dataset or includes typed links resolving to an external metadata resource. 		

2.9 Authentication Support of Protocol for Metadata and Data

FIELD	DESCRIPTION	
Metric Identifier	FsF-A1.2-01MD	
Metric Name	Metadata and data are accessible through a standardized communication protocol which supports authentication	
Description	Given an identifier of a dataset, the metadata of the dataset as well as related data should be retrievable using a standard communication protocol which supports authentication such as HTTP, HTTPS, FTPS	
FAIR Principle	A1: (Meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communication protocol	
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community	
ASSESSMENT		
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data identifier (IRI, URL) 	
Associated F-UJI tests	test	score
	The communication protocol found in identifiers (IRIs) leading to metadata supports authentication	1
	The communication protocol identified in data links (IRIs) supports authentication	1
Scoring mechanism	cumulative, total metric score is calculated as the sum of all test scores	

Assessment	Check the application protocol of the data as well as metadata identifier based on the scheme part of the given IRI. Verify the protocol provides an authentication mechanism based on a lookup table or similar.
COMMENTS	
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples of transport layer security, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Transport_Layer_Security • IANA Protocol Registries, https://www.iana.org/protocols <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Restricted or sensitive datasets may not be retrievable over the Web. Special human to human protocols may be involved and in-person authorization services may be required to retrieve these datasets. 	

2.10 Metadata Preservation

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-A2-01M - suspended
Metric Name	Metadata remains available, even if the data is no longer available.
Description	This metric determines if the metadata will be preserved even when the data they represent are no longer available, replaced or lost. Similar to metric FsF-F4-01M , answering this metric will require an understanding of the capabilities offered, data preservation plan and policies implemented by the data repository and data services (e.g., Datacite PID service). Continued access to metadata depends on a data repository's preservation practice which is usually documented in the repository's service policies or statements. A trustworthy data repository offering DOIs and implementing a Persistence Policy should guarantee that metadata will remain accessible even when data is no longer available for any reason (e.g., by providing a tombstone page)
FAIR Principle	A2. Metadata should be accessible even when the data is no longer available
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R10. The repository assumes responsibility for long-term preservation and manages this function in a planned and documented way
ASSESSMENT	
Requirement(s)	--
Assessment	<p>Currently not possible at the dataset level</p> <p>Programmatic assessment of the preservation of metadata of a data object can only be tested if the object is deleted or replaced. In this case a tombstone page needs to be in place e.g. indicated by a 410 (Gone) HTTP status code. However, such a status code may be returned for various reasons and there is no commonly accepted best practice or standard to indicate tombstone pages in a machine friendly way.</p> <p>Importantly, continued access to metadata depends on a data repository's preservation practice which may be described in a dedicated preservation policy as part of a repository's metadata as recommended by the RDA data repository attributes) working group (DRAWG).</p>

	<p>In general, we regard that the assessment of metric applies to at the level of a repository, not at the level of individual objects. For this reason, we excluded its assessment details from this specification.</p>
COMMENTS	
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● DMPonline, https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/public_plans ● DMP Common Standards WG, https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/dmp-common-standards-wg ● ezDMP, https://ezdmp.org/index ● Best Practices for offering tombstone pages, https://support.datacite.org/docs/tombstone-pages ● RDA DRAWG attributes 10.15497/rda00103 <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data preservation statements are usually found in a repository’s data policy or other governance documents. Machine-actionable representation of preservation policies in repository catalogues and registries such as re3data is important to enable an automated assessment of the statements. Further work in this areas is needed, for example to enable data producers to receive repository recommendations, based on preservation requirements expressed in machine-actionable DMPs, e.g., http://dx.doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v15i1.704 ● Currently, PID providers (e.g., DataCite) do not offer any tombstone pages automatically for unavailable objects. Data providers may maintain the pages instead, for example https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.715333 ● There is no common agreement on how and what metadata should be exposed on a tombstone page, e.g. with respect to the resources type and status. 	

2.11 Formal Representation of Metadata

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-I1-01M
Metric Name	Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language.
Description	Knowledge representation is vital for machine-processing of the knowledge of a domain. Expressing the metadata of a data object using a formal knowledge representation will enable machines to process it in a meaningful way and enable more data exchange possibilities. Examples of knowledge representation languages are RDF, RDFS, and OWL. These languages may be serialized (written) in different formats. For instance, RDF/XML, RDFa, Notation3, Turtle, N-Triples and N-Quads, and JSON-LD are RDF serialization formats.
FAIR Principle	I1. (Meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation Note: The I1 principle loosely defines the use of knowledge representation. Therefore, we define two metrics corresponding to the principle concerning metadata. The metric FsF-I1-01M focuses on making the metadata available for machine-mediated interpretation, whereas the metric FsF-I1-02M focuses on the use of semantic resources to enrich metadata.
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R14. The repository enables reuse of the data over time, ensuring that appropriate metadata are available to support the understanding and use of the data

	R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community								
ASSESSMENT									
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • Metadata provision endpoint (e.g., SPARQL endpoint) 								
Associated F-UJI tests	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Parsable, structured metadata (JSON-LD, RDFa) is embedded in the landing page XHTML/HTML code</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">or</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Parsable, structured metadata (RDF, JSON-LD) is accessible through content negotiation, typed links or SPARQL endpoint</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Parsable, structured metadata (JSON-LD, RDFa) is embedded in the landing page XHTML/HTML code	2	or		Parsable, structured metadata (RDF, JSON-LD) is accessible through content negotiation, typed links or SPARQL endpoint	2
test	score								
Parsable, structured metadata (JSON-LD, RDFa) is embedded in the landing page XHTML/HTML code	2								
or									
Parsable, structured metadata (RDF, JSON-LD) is accessible through content negotiation, typed links or SPARQL endpoint	2								
Scoring mechanism	alternative, total metric score is equal to highest individual test score reached								
Assessment	<p>Machine-actionable representation (e.g., RDF) of the metadata may be retrieved as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If content negotiation is supported, use the identifier to perform a request, e.g., an RDF-based document. • Use the 'typed links' given in the HTML header section of the landing page to access the RDF-based metadata of the data, e.g., https://data.gov.lv/dati/lv/dataset/covid-19 • Query the SPARQL endpoint using the identifier (or optionally title) of the data, for example by using metadata elements from dcterms and DCAT standards. Perform a full text-search within the SPARQL query if it is supported. 								
COMMENTS									
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RDF MIME types by serializer, http://librdf.org/raptor/api/raptor-formats-types-by-serializer.html • SPARQL Protocol for RDF, https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-protocol/ • Best Practice Recipes for Publishing RDF Vocabularies, https://www.w3.org/TR/swbp-vocab-pub/ • Community-defined models and formats via FAIRsharing, https://fairsharing.org/standards/?q=&selected_facets=type_exact:model/format <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Based on a data identifier, it is not possible to programmatically discover the SPARQL endpoint provided by a data repository, unless the endpoint information is specified in the repository metadata, e.g., https://www.re3data.org/repository/r3d100012203 • The RDF-based metadata may not be supported by the data repository which curates the data, but it may be available through external linked data repositories, e.g., bio2rdf. • RDF data may be serialized in a number of different ways. Therefore, the variety of serialization formats (and their respective MIME types) should be considered when performing the SPARQL query. 									

2.12 Metadata with Semantic Resources

FIELD	DESCRIPTION				
Metric Identifier	FsF-I2-01M				
Metric Name	Metadata uses registered semantic resources.				
Description	<p>A metadata document or selected parts of the document may incorporate additional terms from semantic resources (also referred as semantic artefacts) that unambiguously describe the contents so they can be processed automatically by machines. This metadata enrichment may facilitate enhanced data search and interoperability of data from different sources.</p> <p>Ontology, thesaurus, and taxonomy are kinds of semantic resources, and they come with varying degrees of expressiveness and computational complexity. Knowledge organization schemes such as thesaurus and taxonomy are semantically less formal than ontologies. As a base requirement for FAIR semantic resources / vocabularies these should be registered in a semantic repository which supports metadata indexing.</p>				
FAIR Principle	I2. (Meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles				
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	<p>R14. The repository enables reuse of the data over time, ensuring that appropriate metadata are available to support the understanding and use of the data</p> <p>R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community</p>				
ASSESSMENT					
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • Optionally a metadata provision endpoint (SPARQL endpoint) • Machine-accessible and readable metadata • Registry of semantic resources 				
Associated F-UJI tests	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Metadata uses terms from registered vocabularies that are identified by their namespaces</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Metadata uses terms from registered vocabularies that are identified by their namespaces	2
test	score				
Metadata uses terms from registered vocabularies that are identified by their namespaces	2				
Assessment	<p>This assessment is the continuation of the assessment FsF-I1-01M, but focuses on the metadata contents.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extract namespaces declared from the machine-actionable metadata document. Filter out common namespaces (e.g., rdf, rdfs, xsd, owl). • Compare the remaining namespaces with entries from existing (known) ontology registries (see examples listed in Related Resources). 				
COMMENTS					
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publishing and consuming Linked Data embedded in HTML, https://www.w3.org/2001/sw/interest/ldh/ • Examples of repositories or look-up services for semantic resources (the list is not exhaustive): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Linked Open Vocabularies (LOV), https://lov.linkeddata.es/dataset/lov ○ OBO Foundry, http://www.obofoundry.org/ ○ BioPortal, https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ ○ Basel Register of Thesauri, Ontologies & Classifications (BARTOC), https://bartoc.org/ ○ NERC Vocabulary Server, https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/ 					

- Research Vocabulary Australia, <https://vocabs.andis.org.au/>
 - MMI Ontology Registry and Repository (ORR), <https://mmisw.org/>
 - Industrial Ontologies Foundry (IOF), <https://www.industrialontologies.org/>
 - CESSDA Vocabulary Service, <https://vocabularies.cessda.eu/>
- Known Limitations/Constraints**
- The assessment checks the inclusion of semantic markup in the metadata page, not their contents and quality, e.g., if the terms used are in appropriate context and accessible over the web.
 - There is no up-to-date, maintained, cross domain ontology catalogue, registry or ontology library available.

2.13 Qualified References to Related Entities

FIELD	DESCRIPTION								
Metric Identifier	FsF-I3-01M								
Metric Name	Metadata includes qualified references between the data and its related entities								
Description	Linking data to its related entities will increase its potential for reuse. The linking information should be captured as part of the metadata. A dataset may be linked to its prior version, related datasets or resources (e.g. publication, physical sample, funder, repository, platform, site, or observing network registries). Links between data and its related entities should be qualified, thus expressed through relation types (e.g., DataCite Metadata Schema specifies relation types between research objects through the fields 'RelatedIdentifier' and 'RelationType'), and preferably use persistent Identifiers for related entities.								
FAIR Principle	I3. (Meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data								
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R11. The repository has appropriate expertise to address technical data and metadata quality and ensures that sufficient information is available for end users to make quality-related evaluations								
ASSESSMENT									
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Dataset identifier (IRI, URL) ● Machine-accessible and readable metadata 								
Associated F-UJI tests	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Related resources are referenced in plain text within appropriate metadata properties indicating the relation type</td> <td>2</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">or</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Related resources are referenced by machine readable links or identifiers within appropriate metadata properties indicating the relation type</td> <td>2</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Related resources are referenced in plain text within appropriate metadata properties indicating the relation type	2	or		Related resources are referenced by machine readable links or identifiers within appropriate metadata properties indicating the relation type	2
test	score								
Related resources are referenced in plain text within appropriate metadata properties indicating the relation type	2								
or									
Related resources are referenced by machine readable links or identifiers within appropriate metadata properties indicating the relation type	2								
Scoring mechanism	alternative, total metric score is equal to highest individual test score reached								
Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use the data identifier to access its metadata record. ● Check the metadata elements which indicate the relationship between data and related entities. ● Test if the URLs of the related entities are active (not broken links). 								
COMMENTS									

<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DataCite Metadata Working Group. (2019). DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data. Version 4.3, https://doi.org/10.14454/7xq3-zf69 • Link Relation Types, https://www.iana.org/assignments/link-relations/link-relations.xhtml <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different metadata schemas may use different properties to specify the relation between data and its related entities. • The assessment regards any relation between a data and its related entities as success. It does not consider the quantity or types of relations. • Links to related resources are not necessarily expressed as actionable links but may also be strings such as citations.

2.14 Metadata of Data Content

FIELD	DESCRIPTION								
Metric Identifier	FsF-R1-01MD								
Metric Name	Metadata specifies the content of the data.								
Description	<p>This metric evaluates if the content of the dataset is specified in the metadata (beyond the provision of the data identifier), and it should be an accurate reflection of the actual data deposited. Examples of the properties specifying data content are resource type (e.g., data or a collection of data), data format and size. Further, properties like variable(s) measured or observed could be verified, however since these are not available for some data types (images, movies etc.) these should not be scored.</p> <p>Ideally, ontological vocabularies should be used to describe data content (e.g., variable) to support interdisciplinary reuse.</p>								
FAIR Principle	<p>R1: (Meta)data are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes</p> <p>Note: We regard the properties of data content as part of rich metadata in addition to the descriptive metadata evaluated in F2 , therefore we map this metric to its closest principle R1.</p>								
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R11. The repository has appropriate expertise to address technical data and metadata quality and ensures that sufficient information is available for end users to make quality-related evaluations								
ASSESSMENT									
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dataset Identifier • Machine-accessible and readable metadata 								
Associated F-UJI tests	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Minimum information (resource type) about the available data content is specified in the metadata</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Information on the manner and form (file size and type or service (API) endpoint and protocol) in which data is delivered is provided</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Minimum information (resource type) about the available data content is specified in the metadata	1	Information on the manner and form (file size and type or service (API) endpoint and protocol) in which data is delivered is provided	1	Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata	0
test	score								
Minimum information (resource type) about the available data content is specified in the metadata	1								
Information on the manner and form (file size and type or service (API) endpoint and protocol) in which data is delivered is provided	1								
Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata	0								
Scoring mechanism	cumulative, total metric score is calculated as the sum of all test scores								

Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use the data identifier to access its metadata document. ● Identify the resource type given in the metadata ● Verify the presence/absence of elements representing data content descriptions in the metadata document. ● (Optionally) Verify if methods or observed properties (variables) are part of the metadata ● (Optionally) Check if ontology terms are used to describe data content.
COMMENTS	
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Frictionless Data, https://frictionlessdata.io/ ● Data on the Web Best Practice, https://www.w3.org/TR/dwbp/ ● Apache Tika (an example of content analysis toolkit), https://tika.apache.org/ <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Some metadata standards do not allow the inclusion of data content descriptors ● General-purpose metadata standards such as Datacite Metadata Schema and Schema.org are well suited to provide elements to represent content descriptions. 	

2.15 Data Usage License

FIELD	DESCRIPTION				
Metric Identifier	FsF-R1.1-01M				
Metric Name	Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.				
Description	This metric evaluates if data is associated with a license because otherwise users cannot reuse it in a clear legal context. We encourage the application of licenses for all kinds of data whether public, restricted or for specific users. Without an explicit license, users do not have a clear idea of what can be done with your data. Licenses can be of standard type (Creative Commons, Open Data Commons Open Database License) or bespoke licenses, and rights statements which indicate the conditions under which data can be reused. It is highly recommended to use a standard, machine-readable license such that it can be interpreted by machines and humans. In order to inform users about what rights they have to use a dataset, the license information should be specified as part of the dataset's metadata.				
FAIR Principle	R1.1. (Meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license				
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R2. The repository maintains all applicable licenses covering data access and use and monitors compliance				
ASSESSMENT					
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data identifier (IRI, URL) ● Machine-accessible and readable metadata 				
Associated F-UJI tests	<table border="1" style="width: 100%;"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Licence information is given in an appropriate metadata element</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Licence information is given in an appropriate metadata element	1
test	score				
Licence information is given in an appropriate metadata element	1				
Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use the data identifier to access its metadata document. ● Verify the presence/absence of metadata element(s) corresponding to license information of the data. 				

COMMENTS
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SPDX license registry, https://spdx.org/licenses/ ● Rights statements of cultural heritage objects, https://rightsstatements.org/page/1.0/?language=en ● ARDC Data Rights Management Guide, https://ardc.edu.au/guides/research-data-rights-management ● The Landscape of Rights and Licensing Initiatives for Data Sharing, https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2019-029 ● Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL), https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/ ● Creative Commons, https://creativecommons.org/ ● Creative Commons Rights Expression Language, https://creativecommons.org/ns <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The assessment checks if the license information is provided as part of the metadata. It does not validate if the specified license is the most appropriate license for the data. There may be quite specific circumstances related to the data that cannot be explicitly expressed in the metadata as to why a license was chosen.

2.16 Data Provenance

FIELD	DESCRIPTION
Metric Identifier	FsF-R1.2-01M
Metric Name	Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation.
Description	<p>Data provenance (also known as lineage) represents a dataset’s history, including the people, entities, and processes involved in its creation, management and longer-term curation. It is essential to provide provenance information about your data to provide valuable context and to enable informed use and reuse. The levels of provenance information needed can vary depending on the data type (e.g., measurement, observation, derived data, or data product) and research domains. For that reason, it is difficult to define a set of finite provenance properties that will be adequate for all domains. Based on existing work, we suggest that the following provenance properties of data generation or collection are included in the metadata record as a minimum.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sources of data, e.g., datasets and other resources the data is derived from ● Data creation or collection date ● Contributors involved in data creation and their roles ● Data publication, modification and versioning information <p>There are various ways through which provenance information may be included in a metadata record. Provenance information can be given in a linked provenance record expressed explicitly in e.g., PROV-O or PAV or Vocabulary of Interlinked Datasets (VOID). Alternatively suitable metadata properties can be used. For example, Dublin Core has been mapped to PROV in PROV-DC which allows further mappings of other metadata standards to PROV.</p>
FAIR Principle	R1.2. (Meta)data are associated with detailed provenance
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R7. The repository guarantees the integrity and authenticity of the data

ASSESSMENT									
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • Machine-accessible and readable metadata 								
Associated F-UJI tests	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information which can be mapped to PROV based on PROV-DC</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>or</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information using formal provenance ontologies (PROV, PAV)</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information which can be mapped to PROV based on PROV-DC	1	or		Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information using formal provenance ontologies (PROV, PAV)	1
test	score								
Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information which can be mapped to PROV based on PROV-DC	1								
or									
Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information using formal provenance ontologies (PROV, PAV)	1								
Scoring mechanism	alternative, total metric score is equal to highest individual test score reached								
Assessment	<p>Use the data identifier to access its metadata record. Verify the presence/absence of metadata element(s) corresponding to the minimum data provenance properties.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of basic ‘proxy’ metadata elements related to data creation (creator, contributors, date, and version, modification date, etc.) which can be mapped using the PROV-DC example • Presence of process indicator, e.g. dc:source or relation type (isVersionOf, isBasedOn, isFormatOf) addressed in FsF-I3-01M which can be mapped via PROV-DC • Presence of PROV-O or PAV information in RDFa microformats (landing page) or in RDF metadata. 								
COMMENTS									
<p>Related Resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PROV Model Primer, https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-primer/ • PROV-DC Dublin Core to PROV Mapping, https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dc/ • Checklist for Evaluation of Dataset Fitness for Use produced by the WDS/RDA Assessment of Data Fitness for Use WG, https://www.rd-alliance.org/system/files/DataFitnessForUse_ChecklistForm_v2_20181218_RDADistribution.pdf • W3C Recommendation Data on the Web Best Practices (8.4 Data Provenance), https://www.w3.org/TR/dwbp/#metadata • PROV-O as RDFa, https://www.w3.org/2011/prov/wiki/PROV-O_as_RDF • OPMV, the Open Provenance Model Vocabulary, http://purl.org/net/opmv/ns • Business Process Model and Notation, https://www.omg.org/spec/BPMN/ • PAV- Provenance, Authoring and Versioning ontology: https://pav-ontology.github.io/pav/ <p>Known Limitations/Constraints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The proposed minimum provenance properties are not final; new properties may be incorporated into the assessment if the requirement emerges. Properties such as processes/methods (incl. model, instrument, etc.) used in the data creation depend on domain standards. • We regard references to related works (scholarly articles, data papers, preceding or associated data) as useful provenance information. This property of provenance is considered as part of FsF-I3-01M, therefore we excluded it from the assessment. • Metadata may include a specific element (e.g., dcmi:provenance) and/or ‘proxy’ elements (e.g., datacite:Contributor, schema.org:measurementTechnique) to convey data provenance. 									

- Data may be published at different analysis stages (raw, processed, derivative, product). The completeness of the provenance information may depend on the stage at which the data is published.

2.17 Community Metadata Standard

FIELD	DESCRIPTION								
Metric Identifier	FsF-R1.3-01M								
Metric Name	Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data.								
Description	In addition to core metadata required to support data discovery (covered under metric FsF-F2-01M), metadata to support data reusability should be made available following community-endorsed metadata standards. Some communities have well-established metadata standards (e.g., geospatial: ISO19115; biodiversity: DarwinCore, ABCD, EML; social science: DDI; astronomy: International Virtual Observatory Alliance Technical Specifications) while others have limited standards or standards that are under development (e.g., engineering and linguistics). The use of community-endorsed metadata standards is usually encouraged and supported by domain and discipline-specific repositories.								
FAIR Principle	R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards								
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R14. The repository enables reuse of the data over time, ensuring that appropriate metadata are available to support the understanding and use of the data								
ASSESSMENT									
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data identifier (IRI, URL) • Metadata provision endpoints including SPARQL endpoint 								
Associated F-UJI tests	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>test</th> <th>score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Community specific metadata standard is detected using namespaces or schemas found in provided metadata</td> <td>1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>or</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Multidisciplinary but community endorsed metadata (RDA Metadata Standards Catalog, fairsharing) standard is detected by namespace</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Community specific metadata standard is detected using namespaces or schemas found in provided metadata	1	or		Multidisciplinary but community endorsed metadata (RDA Metadata Standards Catalog, fairsharing) standard is detected by namespace	1
test	score								
Community specific metadata standard is detected using namespaces or schemas found in provided metadata	1								
or									
Multidisciplinary but community endorsed metadata (RDA Metadata Standards Catalog, fairsharing) standard is detected by namespace	1								
Scoring mechanism	alternative, total metric score is equal to highest individual test score reached								
Assessment	<p>Gather all metadata records connected to a dataset identifier or landing page URI e.g. via content negotiation or via signposting links.</p> <p>Use namespace identifiers or schema identifiers to identify the metadata standards used.</p> <p>Cross check found standards with an external metadata registry, e.g., RDA Metadata Standards Catalog or fairsharing.</p>								
COMMENTS									
<p>Related Resources</p> <p>Examples of the metadata standards with subject areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DCC List of Metadata Standards, http://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/metadata-standards/list • RDA Metadata Standards Catalog, https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/ • FAIRsharing, https://fairsharing.org/standards/ 									

- Metadata standards supported by a repository may be available through re3data, <https://www.re3data.org/>
- Known Limitations/Constraints**
- Future evaluation of the metric should also consider the extent to which the metadata of a dataset reflects the community-endorsed metadata standard.
 - Some of these discipline-specific standards might not be properly formalized or structured so an automatic validation of the metadata based on the standards can be problematic. External tools might be necessary to check compliance with metadata standards.

2.18 Data File Format

FIELD	DESCRIPTION				
Metric Identifier	FsF-R1.3-02D				
Metric Name	Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.				
Description	File formats refer to methods for encoding digital information. For example, CSV for tabular data, NetCDF for multidimensional data and GeoTIFF for raster imagery. Data should be made available in a file format that is backed by the research community to enable data sharing and reuse. Consider for example, file formats that are widely used and supported by the most commonly used software and tools. These formats also should be suitable for long-term storage and archiving, which are usually recommended by a data repository. The formats not only give a higher certainty that your data can be read in the future, but they will also help to increase the reusability and interoperability. Using community-endorsed formats enables data to be loaded directly into the software and tools used for data analysis. It makes it possible to easily integrate your data with other data using the same preferred format. The use of community-endorsed formats will also help to transform the format to a newer one, in case an older format gets outdated.				
FAIR Principle	R1.3. (Meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards				
CoreTrustSeal Alignment	R14. The repository enables reuse of the data over time, ensuring that appropriate metadata are available to support the understanding and use of the data R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community				
ASSESSMENT					
Requirement(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data identifier (IRI, URL) ● Machine-accessible and readable metadata 				
Compliance Levels	<table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <thead> <tr> <th style="width: 80%;">test</th> <th style="width: 20%;">score</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Data is available in a file format recommended by the research community (long term file formats, open file formats or scientific file format)</td> <td style="text-align: center;">1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	test	score	Data is available in a file format recommended by the research community (long term file formats, open file formats or scientific file format)	1
test	score				
Data is available in a file format recommended by the research community (long term file formats, open file formats or scientific file format)	1				
Assessment	Extract file format information (mime-type) from the metadata based on elements, e.g., datacite:Format, schema.org: fileFormat, dc:format. Check if the format is an open and long-term file format (see comment* below).				
COMMENTS					
Related Resources					

- A list of commonly used as well as domain specific scientific file formats
 - http://justsolve.archiveteam.org/index.php/Scientific_Data_formats
 - [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_file_formats#Scientific_data_\(data_exchange\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_file_formats#Scientific_data_(data_exchange))
- Examples of recommended file formats based on data types, <https://www.ukdataservice.ac.uk/manage-data/format/recommended-formats.aspx>
- PRONOM file format registry, <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/PRONOM/Format/proFormatSearch.aspx?status=new>
- A recommended format statement by the US Library of Congress, <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/resources/rfs>
- Long-term file formats: ISO/TR 22299. Document management - Digital file format recommendations for long-term storage, <https://www.iso.org/standard/73117.html>
- File type support lists provided by open source and commercial statistics (e.g. https://de.mathworks.com/help/matlab/import_export/supported-file-formats.html) or spreadsheet processing software vendors (e.g. <https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/file-formats-that-are-supported-in-excel-0943ff2c-6014-4e8d-aaea-b83d51d46247?ui=en-us&rs=en-us&ad=us>).

Known Limitations/Constraints

- *At present, there is a lack of reference resources (registries) against which a file format test can be checked programmatically. Common file formats endorsed by communities are not available through a registry but on static web pages (see resources above). This is an issue for the scientific community as a whole. Further work is needed to develop a standard approach to defining which formats are open and suitable for long-term preservation and use and managing those community-specific lists over time.
- Not all data can be made available in an open, non-proprietary, widely supported format, such as most 3D data, CAD data, dynamic spreadsheets or databases with specific significant characteristics which cannot be exported.
- Standard formats in earth system modeling (atmosphere, ocean) are netCDF and GRIB. GRIB is used for internal storage rather than for publication.
- Commonly used community file formats are not necessarily very domain specific. Some very generic file formats for e.g. spreadsheets are widely used by the scientific community.
- Data files may be made available using an archive file format (e.g., *.zip). In addition to the archive format, the actual file formats should be specified in the metadata such that machines can extract/unzip the downloaded file and read the actual files programmatically.
- Many scientific formats do not have an associated mime-type (e.g. BUFR), thus are hard to detect.

Appendix

To date, a large number of users from the scientific community have used F-UJI to perform FAIR assessments on data sets from a wide variety of fields. Consequently, these activities provided plenty of feedback on the tool and metricse.g. via the Github issues or through direct contact with us by email or in face-to-face dialogue during conferences and meetings. Some users in addition have published their experiences with the tool and the underlying FAIRsFAIR (FsF) metrics in a number of articles. These include works that have presented a detailed analysis of FAIR metrics from different FAIR assessment tools. And finally, in the course of developing discipline-specific metrics, these and the underlying domain-independent metrics were thoroughly examined by experts in the field. We therefore now have a large number of well-founded input and suggestions regarding the FsF metrics used by F-UJI and the associated practical tests, which are very well suited to improving them and harmonising them with the metrics used by other FAIR assessment tools. Several authors complained about the differing number of metrics for each FAIR principle and different number of tests per metric which makes it difficult to compare FAIR assessment results (e.g. Gehlen et al. 2022, Moser et al., 2023). Detailed comparative analyses of metrics and tests for each FAIR principle have been provided by Sun et al, 2022 , Moser et al., 2023, Aguilar, 2023 and Candela et al, 2024 which revealed considerable differing FAIR metric coverage between several tools and their metrics respectively. Their findings enabled us to identify some issues related to previous versions of the FsF metrics.

Overview of the changes to the FAIR metric from version 0.5 to version 0.8 and detailed justification with reference to the literature sources taken into account:

Findable:

FsF-F1:

Moser, Aguilar noticed the differing coverage of data and metadata in F-UJI for FAIR principle F1 which claims to focus on the data aspect only (FsF-F1-D). Here it has to be noticed that the FsF metrics used the 'D' identifier to indicate the data set itself and did not differentiate between data and metadata which is confusing in particular since we did not test identifiers for data (e.g. downloadable files or data streams) here.

We therefore will rename FsF-F1-D to FsF-F1-MD so it clearly indicates its purpose to test both, for identifiers which link to metadata or landing pages as well as to data.

Further for the sake of simplicity, we merge the two tests for D1 and instead provide one test which tests for UUID, HASH and URL, IRI in one step. Unique identifiers also include persistent identifiers tested in F1-02, which needs to be mentioned in the test title and description.

FsF-F1-01D-1: Candela et al. comment on the verification step which is claimed in the test which is described as 'Identifier is resolvable and follows a defined unique identifier syntax' this rather relates to FAIR principle A1 which is true if taking the test description literally. We however did test the syntax only and 'resolvable' served to distinguish between actionable (http etc) and non-actionable identifiers.

Therefore we will rename this test e.g. 'Data identifier follows a defined unique identifier syntax or scheme' In addition we will add additional tests which will focus on the identification of unique identifiers in data (see table below).

FsF-F1-02D-2 (Persistent identifier is resolvable): Here we however think verifying the URL resolution of a PID is necessary because this is the only (or easiest) way to verify a PID actually exists, thus is registered and maintained by a PID authority. To clarify this purpose we will rename the test to: 'Persistent identifier is registered and maintained by a PID authority proved by redirection' to clearly distinguish this test from A1

(which tests resolution to metadata or data), we will not test if a PID resolves but if it is redirected by the PID system, thus the first HTTP status delivered is a 30x.

For metrics <= 0.5 F-UJI additionally verifies if the PID resolves to the domain of the data provider. This is e.g. important in case PIDs are indicated in metadata of a data set only. We however agree with Candela, that this test might be out of scope of FAIR and therefore will provide an additional test 'FsF-F1-02D-3 Persistent identifier resolves to a page which belongs to the issuer's domain' which we will however not score. This test will however raise warning messages, so it becomes clear to the tester if e.g. PIDs are wrongly claimed for a data set.

v0.5 ID	score	v0.5 title	v0.8 ID	score	v0.8 title
FsF-F1-01D-1	1	Identifier is resolvable and follows a defined unique identifier syntax (IRI, URL)	FsF-F1-01MD-1	1	Metadata identifier follows a defined unique identifier syntax or scheme (IRI, URL, UUID, HASH or PID)
FsF-F1-01D-2	or 4	Identifier is not resolvable but follows an UUID or HASH type syntax			
			FsF-F1-01MD-2	0	Data identifier follows a defined unique identifier syntax or scheme (IRI, URL, UUID, HASH or PID)
FsF-F1-02D-1	0.5	Identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax	FsF-F1-02MD-1	0.5	Metadata identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax
FsF-F1-02D-2	0.5	Persistent identifier is resolvable	FsF-F1-02MD-2	0.5	Persistent identifier for metadata is registered and maintained by a PID authority
					D2: resolution to owner domain no longer tested
			FsF-F1-02MD-4	0	Data identifier follows a defined persistent identifier syntax
			FsF-F1-02MD-5	0	Persistent identifier for data is registered and maintained by a PID authority

Table 2: Changes for the F1 FAIR principle, blue: changes, green: new, orange: deleted

FsF-F2:

FsF-F2-01M-1 (Metadata has been made available via common web methods): Candela correctly notes this test rather fits to FAIR principle A1 and we agree in their opinion. Therefore, we will not include this test in metrics after version 0.5.

FsF-F2-01M-1	0.5	Metadata has been made available via common web methods			
FsF-F2-01	0.5	Core data citation metadata is available	FsF-F2-01	1	Core data citation metadata is

M-2			M-2		available
FsF-F2-01 M-3	1	Core descriptive metadata is available	FsF-F2-01 M-3	1	Core descriptive metadata is available

FsF-F3:

FsF-F3-01M-1 (Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)): Candela et al. correctly comment that this test is rather related to R (R3) and, this test seems to be a duplicate of what is tested already in FsF-R1-01MD-1. This was also remarked by colleagues from CESSDA. Therefore the test will not be performed in metrics > 0.5

FsF-F3-01M-1	0.5	Metadata contains data content related information (file name, size, type)			
FsF-F3-01M-2	0.5	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content	FsF-F3-01M-2	1	Metadata contains a PID or URL which indicates the location of the downloadable data content

FsF-F4:

FsF-F4-01M-1: Candela et al. relate this test to principle I1 probably because of the misleading test title which mentions a list of formats which led Candela et al to comment “it leverages a serialisation point of view”. The metric however focuses on methods to expose metadata in a search engine friendly way which includes metadata formats but also the way how it is exposed to search engines. We therefore will rename this test so it becomes clear that it verifies the presence of search-engine friendly metadata as a proxy for search engine inclusion. This is in particular Dublin Core or schema.org or DCAT encoded in microdata, RDFa, embedded JSON-LD or meta tags. We are aware that this is only a proxy to check the inclusion of metadata records in large search engine catalogs, but given the lack of availability (or reliability) of search engine APIs, this seems like a reasonable way to test F4 compatibility.

FsF-F4-01M-2: Because checking whether a dataset is indexed in registers such as DataCite, Mendeley and especially Google Dataset Search is very error-prone, due to the missing availability and stability of search engine APIs this test will not no longer be performed in metrics > 0.5.

FsF-F4-01M-1	1	Metadata is given in a way major search engines can ingest it for their catalogues (JSON-LD, Dublin Core, RDFa)	FsF-F4-01M-1	2	Metadata is given in a way major search engines can ingest it for their catalogues (Dublin Core or schema.org or DCAT encoded in microdata, RDFa, embedded JSON-LD or meta tags see e.g. Google Dataset Search webmaster guidelines)
FsF-F4-01M-2	4	Metadata is registered in major research data registries (DataCite)			

Accessible

FsF-A1:

FsF-A1-01M-1 is testing for the presence of access rights in metadata. Candela et al rather locate this at R1, but since we follow the RDA logic, we’ll leave this metric in A. However the test 2 and 3 are requiring the usage of a limited set of terminologies to describe access status which might be to restrictive and rather be

part of data/metadata quality testing. We therefore exclude these two tests from version 0.8.

We agree with Candela et al that A1 in general should focus on the **‘retrievable’** aspect, which means to test if metadata and data are retrievable via their identifiers anyway.

We therefore add a new test: **FsF-A1-02MD** Metadata and data are retrievable by their identifier.

Tests for FsF-A1-02M and FsF-A1-02D rather focus on the protocol aspect and not the retrievability aspect of A1, we therefore will change the identifier for these protocol related metrics and test to better model the original FAIR principles.

In contrast to A1, A1.1 and A1.2. are focussing on protocol issues. In prior versions of the FsF metrics we included these tests to A1, but as Sun et al (2022), Moser et al. (2023) and Aguilar et al. (2023) correctly identified this results in a mapping problem with other metrics and assessment tools which is problematic. Therefore we will rename e.g. FsF-A1-02M1 to **FsF-A1.1-01MD-1** and FsF-A1-03D-1 to **FsF-A1.1-01MD-2**. As a result, instead of having separate metrics for data and metadata we will only use one metric labeled as **FsF-A1.1-01MD** (replacing FsF-A1-02M and FsF-A1-03D) which will consist of separate tests for data and metadata.

The associated tests for these metrics will not test resolution or retrievability or presence of metadata which is already done in A1.

Further, we introduce additional metrics and tests which explicitly focus on the authentication aspect, the metric will be labelled as **FsF-A1.2-01MD**.

FsF-A1-01M-1	0.5	Information about access restrictions or rights can be identified in metadata	FsF-A1-01M-1	1	Information about access restrictions or rights can be identified in metadata
FsF-A1-01M-2	0.5	Data access information is machine readable			
FsF-A1-01M-3	1	Data access information is indicated by (not machine readable) standard terms			
			FsF-A1-02M D-1	0.5	Metadata are retrievable via their specified identifier
			FsF-A1-02M D-2	0.5	Data are retrievable via the identifiers given in metadata
FsF-A1-02M-1	1	Landing page link is based on standardized web communication protocols.	FsF-A1.1-01 MD-1	0.5	Identifier leading to metadata matches a scheme indicating a standardized web communication protocol
FsF-A1-03D-1	1	Metadata includes a resolvable link to data based on standardized web communication protocols	FsF-A1.1-01 MD-2	0.5	Identifier leading to data are matching a schema indicating a standardized web communication protocol
			FsF-A1.2-01 MD-1	0.5	The communication protocol found in identifiers (IRIs) leading to metadata supports authentication
			FsF-A1.2-01	0.5	The communication protocol

			MD-2	identified in data links (IRIs) supports authentication
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Interoperable

FsF-I1

FsF-I1-01M-2: The title of this test is a bit confusing, since it does not explicitly refer to structured data, so we will rename this test accordingly.

Since it has correctly been remarked that delivering the (potentially) same content in two ways does not justify a higher score (<https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/fuji/issues/507>) we will change the scoring method here so both methods to expose structured data will equally be scored.

FsF-I1-01M-1	1	Parsable, structured metadata (JSON-LD, RDFa) is embedded in the landing page XHTML/HTML code	FsF-I1-01M-1	2	Parsable, structured metadata (JSON-LD, RDFa) is embedded in the landing page XHTML/HTML code
		and			or
FsF-I1-01M-2	1	Parsable, graph data (RDF, JSON-LD) is accessible through content negotiation, typed links or SPARQL endpoint	FsF-I1-01M-2	2	Parsable, structured metadata (RDF, JSON-LD) is accessible through content negotiation, typed links or SPARQL endpoint

FsF-I2

FsF-I2-01M-1 and **FsF-I2-01M-2:** Both tests are verifying the presence of URIs pointing to vocabulary terms. However, the two tests are very similar and should be merged, in particular since M-1 is not scored in v0.5 anyway. Candela maps FsF-I2-01M-2 with I3 because they think it checks links to other semantic resources (instead of vocabularies), thus would be a relation. The test however tries to identify namespaces in given term URIs, and is checking if these namespaces are known, which means they are listed in vocabulary registries or lists. Such registration requires a basic set of identifying metadata of these vocabularies as a prerequisite for vocab FAIRness.

We will therefore merge M1 and M2 within test FsF-I2-01M-2 and rename the test so this is clearly indicated.

FsF-I2-01M-1	0	Vocabulary namespace URIs can be identified in metadata			
FsF-I2-01M-2	1	Namespaces of known semantic resources can be identified in metadata	FsF-I2-01M-2	2	Metadata uses terms from registered vocabularies that are identified by their namespaces

FsF-I3

FsF-I3-01M-1: We rename this test so it becomes clear that related resources are indicated in metadata as plain text in contrast to machine actionable links or identifiers as which is tested in M-2.

FsF-I3-01M-2 and **FsF-I3-01M-1:** In addition, for both test, we clarify that appropriate metadata properties have to be used indicating the relation type (=qualified relation/reference)

FsF-I3-01M-1	1	Related resources are explicitly mentioned in metadata	FsF-I3-01M-1	2	Related resources are referenced in plain text within appropriate metadata properties indicating the relation type
FsF-I3-01M-2	or 1	Related resources are indicated by machine readable links or identifiers	FsF-I3-01M-2	or 2	Related resources are referenced by machine readable links or identifiers within appropriate metadata properties indicating the relation type

FsF-R1

According to Wilkinson et al, specify R1 as "... factors [that] may be needed to determine whether a resource is suitable for inclusion in an analysis, and how to adequately process it." However, this purpose is difficult to distinguish from F2 intent.

In contrast, several R1 in metrics <= 0.5 test are testing data quality issues and veracity of given information in metadata. These tests should not be scored but probably still (silently) be performed in the background.

These tests are **FsF-R1-01MD-3** and **FsF-R1-01MD-4** which are checking eg. if the given file type in metadata matches the mime of the data file are silently performed but not scored nor indicated in the result output. Because we will then exclusively focus on the information given in metadata, we will change the identifiers accordingly to e.g. **FsF-R1-01M** instead of **FsF-R1-01MD**.

In metric v0.5 **FsF-R1-01MD-1** is split in some subtests which can be skipped or merged. E.g FsF-R1-01MD-1b "Information about data content (e.g. links) is given in metadata" is currently not scored and obviously a duplicate of **FsF-F3-01M-2**. Therefore, this test will be changed to **FsF-R1-01M-1** (*Minimum information (resource type) about the available data content is specified in the metadata*) so it becomes clear this test is focussing on resource type indication in metadata. This test no longer matches the resource type against a list of known terms.

Similarly in metric v. 0.5 **FsF-R1-01MD-2** is also divided into several subtests (file info, measured variables), but they are so different that it is better to run them as separate, individual tests (as **FsF-R1-01M-3** and **FsF-R1-01M-4**, see table below).

We therefore change id and title of **FsF-R1-01MD-2** to **FsF-R1-01M-2** (*Information on the manner and form (file size and type or service endpoint and protocol) in which data is delivered is provided*) which will focus on the metadata which describes which and how data actually is provided (file size, type, API info). Further, we added a new test **FsF-R1-01M-3** which focuses on metadata describing what actually has been observed or measured (variables). However, since measured variables cannot be given for every kind of data set or data object (e.g. movies) this test is not scored. Another reason to not score this test is that it actually might better fit to F2.

FsF-R1-01MD-1	1	Minimal information about available data content is given in metadata	FsF-R1-01M-1	1	Minimum information (resource type) about the available data content is specified in the metadata
FsF-R1-01MD-1a		Resource type (e.g. dataset) is given in metadata	merged in M-1		

FsF-R1-01MD-4b		Information about data content (e.g. links) is given in metadata			
FsF-R1-01MD-2	1	Verifiable data descriptors (file info, measured variables or observation types) are specified in metadata	FsF-R1-01M-2	1	Information on the manner and form (file size and type or service (API) endpoint and protocol) in which data is delivered is provided
FsF-R1-01MD-2a		File size and type information are specified in metadata	merged in M-2		
FsF-R1-01MD-2b		Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata	FsF-R1-01M-3	0	Measured variables or observation types are specified in metadata
FsF-R1-01MD-2c		Data service endpoint and protocol information are specified in metadata	merged in M-2		
FsF-R1-01MD-3	4	Data content matches file type and size or protocol specified in metadata	silently performed without scoring		
FsF-R1-01MD-4	4	Data content matches measured variables or observation types specified in metadata	silently performed without scoring		

FsF-R1.1: For licence test, we agree with Candela et al, that verification of licence is rather related to data quality checks and probably out of scope for FAIR tests However, since not every metadata format has a specific 'licence' property and very often a 'rights' property is used to provide license information, some license verification or identification steps have to be performed anyway. We will therefore test **FsF-R1.1-01M-2** of v.0.5 in the background only in versions ≥ 0.8 without scoring but continue to issue relevant logger messages.

FsF-R1.1-01M-1	1	Licence information is given in an appropriate metadata element	FsF-R1.1-01M-1	1	Licence information is given in an appropriate metadata element
FsF-R1.1-01M-2	4	Recognized licence is valid (community specific or registered at SPDX)			

FsF-R1.2 Candela et al. primarily map **FsF-R1.2-01M-2** to I2 and to R1.2 because of the vocab centric nature of the test. In addition, we received some pers. com. feedback in the past from users indicating that the difference between exposing provenance data expressed in PROV versus within metadata properties mapped using PROV-DC is minimal. Therefore, we will score these two R1.2 tests *alternatively* so both tests will receive the same score which will no longer be summed.

FsF-R1.2-01M-1	1	Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information and can be mapped to PROV	FsF-R1.2-01M-1	1	Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information which can be mapped to PROV-O based on PROV-DC
	and			or	

FsF-R1.2-01M-2	1	Metadata contains provenance information using formal provenance ontologies (PROV-O)	FsF-R1.2-01M-2	1	Metadata contains elements which hold provenance information using formal provenance ontologies (PROV-O, PAV)
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FsF-R1.3 Two tests make use of information which are actually rather related to the capabilities of the data repository providing the dataset. In particular, information retrieved from re3data or metadata services such as OAI-PMH are surely helpful to assess the quality of the data provider but these may differ from the quality or FAIRness exposed at the dataset level, for example metadata standards detected or claimed at re3data may not be accessible via a given PID or URI of a distinct dataset. We therefore will perform these tests only silently in versions ≥ 0.8 but not display or score information which is repository related. Instead we will provide appropriate quality related logger messages which would indicate that e.g. a metadata standard claimed to be supported by the data provider is not accessible via the landing page of the PID. All tests will be performed on metadata only, information from re3data entries and service outputs will not be included in test results.

FsF-R1.3-01M-1	1	Community specific metadata standard is detected using namespaces or schemas found in provided metadata or metadata services outputs	FsF-R1.3-01M-1	1	Community specific metadata standard is detected using namespaces or schemas found in provided metadata
FsF-R1.3-01M-2	or 4	Community specific metadata standard is listed in the re3data record of the responsible repository			
FsF-R1.3-01M-3	or 1	Multidisciplinary but community endorsed metadata (RDA Metadata Standards Catalog) standard is listed in the re3data record or detected by namespace	FsF-R1.3-01M-3	or 1	Multidisciplinary but community endorsed metadata (RDA Metadata Standards Catalog) standard is detected by namespace
FsF-R1.3-02D-1	1	The format of a data file given in the metadata is listed in the long term file formats, open file formats or scientific file formats controlled list	FsF-R1.3-02D-1	1	Data is available in a file format recommended by the research community (long term file formats, open file formats or scientific file format)

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